

LONG-TERM SUSTAINABILITY OF ORGANIC FARMING IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGES

Irina Simona AIONESĂ

Mountain Economy Center, CE-MONT/"Costin C. Kirițescu"
Național Institute of Economic Research/Romanian Academy,
Street: Petreni, No. 49, 725700, Vatra Dornei, România.
E-mail: aionesairina21@gmail.com

Abstract

Climate changes represent a current reality, and its effects are intensifying at an ever-increasing pace. The main cause of climate change is the burning of fossil fuels, but also other human activities, such as agriculture, which have a significant impact on this matter. This is one of the reasons why organic farming is a current priority. This requires a healthy, balanced and sustainable food system, it does not contradict traditional agriculture, it only brings some improvements to traditional methods. The European Union is recognized worldwide for its food and culinary traditions, being one of the leading producers of agri-food products and due to its agricultural resources, the EU must play a key-role in ensuring global food security. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) has a key-role to play in supporting the agricultural sector. This article is focusing on a few objectives that are essential for protecting the environment, integrating European strategies for durable development and implementing it on a national level. The results of the analysis that have been made indicate the potential and the importance of this sector – organic farming in lowering the effects on climate change. Organic farming is an important tool in managing the transition to a healthy and balanced food system, it helps fight the effects of climate change and protects the environment. The European Commission, in accordance with the European Green Deal, has adopted the Farm to Fork Strategy and the one regarding biodiversity, which proposes EU actions and commitments to maintain biodiversity in Europe, around the world and the transition to a more sustainable, balanced and healthy food system, as well as improving the livelihoods of all operators involved in the food value chain.

Keywords: *sustainability, organic farming, food system, biodiversity, conversion.*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a current reality, affecting mankind on a global scale, and its effects are acknowledged by decision-taking factors and most of the population.

The effects of climate changes vary from temperature increase, water level increase, extreme weather phenomena, and others. As a result, these changes can have disastrous consequences, landslides, vegetation fires and floods being only a few. The main driver of climate change is the greenhouse effect, and its main causes are the burning of fossil fuels, deforestation and animal raising.

Agriculture is vulnerable and affected by climate change, while at the same time having a big impact to it by growing the greenhouse effect gases.

Risk factors that determine the degree of vulnerability of the health of the populations are: insufficient soil moisture, frequent floods, uneven distribution of rainfall, high temperatures. Only a sustainable agricultural system can ensure global food production by mitigating negative effects of climate change.

The accentuated demographic growth creates an increasing demand for agri-food products, leading to the need to practice a modern agriculture, focused on technology and

quantity. The intensive use of technological means requires a high consumption of fossil fuels – the main culprit for the greenhouse effect. Finding a balance is required, by reducing impact on the climate, maintaining the quality level of food production and generating a quantity of food consistent with the population growth. This balance can be maintained through the use of organic farming, hence the need and urgency implements sets of strategies targeting all levels of human activity, to lower and even counteract these phenomena.

Organic farming can not only adapt to the effects of climate change by choosing alternative agricultural practices, but also has the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the agricultural sector. (Khanal, 2009)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To create this article, the indirect research technique was used, consulting various sources by collecting and processing information from articles addressing similar topics, based on scientific research published so far and online available information (official and specialty sites). This material presents a brief analysis of the importance of organic farming in the context of climate change affecting humanity at an alarming rate worldwide.

Organic farming is seen increasingly more as a sustainable solution for more of the political problems standing in front of agriculture, both in developed and in developing countries. The idea of sustainable agriculture started contouring its bases from 1920, starting from the fundamental idea of working with natural systems, without affecting the environment. Research centers for developing this domain of organic products have been created. The oldest association in Europe, in Great Britain, has been founded in 1946 – the Soil Association, and has been focused on the interconnections between environment quality, population health and the way the food was obtained.

Sustainability is playing an increasingly important role in the long-term functioning and development of human society. According to the Brundtland Report, sustainability is defined as the ability to meet “the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland 1987:41)

In 1972, it is realized that the economic and social developments of mankind are not independent of the environment and that human activities contribute to the long-term degradation of the environment and lead to the depletion of natural resources. These trends and the economic problems threatening humanity are reported in the “Meadows Report” of the Club of Rome, entitled “Limits of Growth”.

These issues of sustainable development have taken on a global political dimension and for the first time at the international level are discussed issues such as environmental degradation, pollution, destruction of resources, the danger of loss of biodiversity through the extinction of plant and animal species due to human activities, at the 1972 United Nations Conference on the Environment in Stockholm.

Later, in 1983, the United Nations established the “World Commission on Environment and Development”, with the aim of studying the dynamics of environmental depreciation and finding solutions to the long-term viability of the human population. This commission was chaired by Gro Harlem Brundtland, the Prime Minister of Norway, from that period where the name “Brundtland Commission” has remained in history.

The Brundtland Commission raises two major issues:

- Development means not only higher profits and higher living standards for a certain category of the population, but increasing the standard of living of all.
- Development means not only higher profits and higher living standards for a certain category of the population, but increasing the standard of living of all.

In 1987, the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) drafted and published the Brundtland Report, also called "Our Common Future", which set out the framework for Agenda 21 and the principles of the Rio Declaration in June 1992.

During the 2005 World Summit – “Millennium Development Goals” (MDGs) on social development the following sustainable development goals have been identified: economic development, social development and environmental protection. Being considered three pillars of sustainability are not mutually exclusive and can be mutually reinforcing. These pillars are interdependent, including long-term.

Organic farming

Synthetic chemical fertilizers are widely used worldwide to increase food production and to feed a continuously growing population. Excessive and irrational use can have a negative effect on the environment as well as harm plant, animal and population health. This is why it is necessary to use mainly organic farming, which ensures a constant balance between the volume of raw materials and the protection of the environment, focusing exclusively on the use of fertilizers and pesticides that are considered organic and which strictly exclude or restrict the use of various methods, including synthetic chemicals, plant growth regulators (such as hormones), the use of antibiotics in animals, or genetically modified organisms (European Commission, 2014)

The International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM, 2008) defines organic farming as “a production system that supports the health of soils, ecosystems and people. It is based on ecological systems, biodiversity and life cycles adapted to local conditions, instead of using inputs with adverse effects. Organic farming combines tradition, innovation and science for the benefit of the environment and promotes fair relations, as well as a good quality of life for all involved”.

The principles of health, ecology, fairness and administration are the base for the development of organic agriculture. (according to IFOAM, 2014)

Table 1. Basic principles of organic farming

Basic principles of organic farming	
Principle of Health	“Organic agriculture should sustain and enhance the health of soil, plant, animal, human and planet as one and indivisible.”
Principle of Ecology	“Organic agriculture should be based on living ecological systems and cycles, work with them, emulate them and help sustain them.”
Principle of Fairness	“Organic agriculture should build on relationships that ensure fairness with regard to the common environment and life opportunities.”
Principle of Administration	“Organic agriculture should build on relationships that ensure fairness with regard to the common environment and life opportunities.”

Source: IFOAM

The most common definition of organic farming is "a holistic production management system that promotes and improves the health of agroecosystems, including biodiversity, biological cycles and soil biological activity" (FAO and WHO, 2001).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The role of organic farming is to produce food more suitable for human metabolism, in full correlation with the conservation and development of the environment. The term "organic agriculture", protected and assigned to Romania by EU, is similar to the terms used in other member states and is practiced especially on smaller farms. Organic farms are mostly smaller in size due to the requirements of the organic system or may be more likely to be organic for economic reasons because they contribute to the growth of important value-added economic activities. A UK study showed that organic farming was often more prevalent in areas less suitable for intensive arable agriculture, characterized by high altitudes and a sloped terrain where the size of the farm is small and the farms are mixed (crop cultivation combined with animal husbandry) (Gabriel et al., 2009).

Livestock farms in the mountain area have an important role due to animal grazing and feed production, thus preventing reforestation (Tasser et al. 2007). and also the impact on the environment and biodiversity, but also ensures the preservation of the traditional landscape and the attractiveness of the region for agrotourism (Bernués et al. 2011; Battaglini et al. 2014 cited in Kühl et al., 2020)

Several researchers highlight the direct impact of organic farming on biodiversity at all levels and the huge role that socio-economic and political factors have on the functioning of agricultural systems.

Some characteristics of pastures play an important role in food chains, such as some species in rich grasslands that contain polyphenols and are also found in dairy products (Duru et al., 2017). Also, species-rich grasslands are a source of feed that can lower methane emissions compared to specific monocultures (Hammond et al., 2014)

Foods that come from small mountain farms and use traditional production methods are associated with a higher quality and nutritional value compared to other products, while promoting environmental sustainability, landscape biodiversity and animal welfare (Farrugia et al. 2014)

An organic farm can make competitive profits by pursuing a low-cost strategy and by increasing the market value of products, such as organic products, "mountain products".

Stability of food production is important for maintaining food security, and genetic diversity in agriculture is fundamental to the resilience of the agro-ecosystem (Frison et al. 2011; Jarvis et al. 2011). Resilience can be understood as a system that retains its organizational capacity and productivity following a disruption. It is a "resistant" agro-ecosystem the one that maintains its ability to supply food production, even when it is disturbed by extreme climatic phenomena, such as periods of drought or heavy rainfall. (Miguel A. Altieri et al., 2015)

Grasslands are agricultural habitats that generate a low-cost source of feed for animals, especially through grazing. Grasslands are increasingly recognized for providing ecosystems, including regulating soil fertility and maintaining nutrient cycles, soil conservation, weed resistance, pollination and pest control, often at higher stages than arable crops. (Cameron, 2013).

At farm level, sustainable intensification means increasing agricultural yields by using the same or a smaller amount of wells and reducing the negative effects on agricultural production and the environment. (Franks, 2014).

Others argue that the strategy of “ecological intensification” of crop production systems, meaning the management and use of ecosystem services provided by biodiversity, is the best choice to sustainably meet future food demand, while reducing the negative effects on the environment. (Ponisio et al. 2015).

By enhancing agricultural production, lowering negative impact on the environment, ensuring decent income for the farmers and satisfying consumer demand, this agricultural sector is feasible (Garbach et al. 2016). The agricultural sector must become a growth factor for the national economy and ensure enough workplaces and guaranteed income for rural population, in order to avoid workforce migration towards urban and metropolitan areas.

In disadvantaged areas, UE grants and subsidies contributed in implementing strategies, technological development of farms and increasing the number of farms in mountain areas, and a relative stability of farmer’s income (Terres et al., 2015; Veysset et al., 2019). About the CAP grants dependency, numerous specialty studies have been completed, for example in France, CAP grants and subsidies have been imported from the beginning for maintaining cattle farms, having influenced farm profitability, work productivity, in a moment that was recording low income per capita (Veysset et al., 2019). At European level, CAP had a significant contribution, by creating an economic dependency of the grants, livestock number increase and reducing needed workforce, lowering variable costs, at the same time with an increase in grazing time and a change of productive orientation (Muñoz-Ulecia et al., 2021).

EU strategies for sustainable development

The European Union is recognized worldwide for its food and culinary traditions, being one of the leading producers of agri-food products and due to its agricultural resources, the EU must play a key role in ensuring global food security.

The European Commission presented in May 2020, the new Biodiversity Strategy 2030 in compliance with the mandatory objectives for saving biodiversity. In June 2021, the European Parliament adds a position regarding the EU's 2030 Biodiversity Strategy: Bringing Nature Back to Our Lives to ensure that by 2050 the world's ecosystems are protected, restored and sustainable.

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) has a key role to play in supporting the EU's agricultural sector. The organic farming sector is an important tool in managing the transition to healthy and balanced food systems, contributing to climate goals and protecting the environment.

The “Farm to Consumer” strategy has as its main goal the use of sustainable food systems by reducing global greenhouse gas emissions, efficient management of natural resources, conservation of biodiversity and maintaining economic efficiency.

The European Commission, in accordance with the European Green Agreement, has adopted the “From Farm to Consumer” Strategies and the “Biodiversity” Strategy, which proposes EU actions and commitments to maintain biodiversity in Europe and around the world and the transition to a more sustainable, balanced and healthy food system, as well as improving the livelihoods of all operators involved in the food value chain.

Fig. 1. "From Farm to Consumer" Strategy

Source: https://ec.europa.eu/food/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en

The Organic Farming Action Plan proposed by the Commission is a key tool for the agricultural sector and aims to increase demand for organic products, maintain consumer confidence in healthy and high quality products and reach the target of 25% of total agricultural land for organic farming in the EU., by 2030. Another key tool is to strengthen organic production in the fight against climate change, maintain biodiversity and efficient management of natural resources (water, air, soil).

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), in addition to the key instruments proposed above, will further support the development of organic farming through rural development programs by providing subsidies for the conversion from conventional to organic farming and long-term maintenance of land in the organic/ecological system.

When The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was born, there were only a few objectives regarding agricultural productivity, the living standards of agricultural producers and the stability of the agricultural market, as it is mentioned on the Treaty for the Functioning of The European Union. As time passed by, from the initial objectives established only for production, farmers and consumers, in 2018 there were nine modern objectives by assimilating social, economic and environment protection aspects. The EU members, in developing strategic planning, will have as a basis the nine objectives imposed by CAP.

For the CAP 2023–2027, this objectives are oriented towards social, economic and environment protection aspects. These include:

1. Supporting viable agricultural income and resiliency in EU;
2. Enhancing market orientation and increasing competitiveness;
3. Enhancing farmer positions in the value chain;
4. Contribution to lowering and adaptation to climate changes;
5. Encouraging sustainable development and efficient natural resources management;
6. Contribution to protecting biodiversity, enhancing eco systemic services and conserving habitats and landscapes;

7. Attracting young farmers and encouraging and facilitating business development in rural areas;
8. Promoting workforce occupation, increasing social inclusion and local development in rural areas;
9. Enhancing UE agricultural response to society demands regarding health and food, including safety and durability.

European Commission action plan regarding organic production development is to increase population consumption of organic products, stimulating production and sustainability of this agricultural sector, and also developing aquaculture in organic procedures.

The European Commission plan for organic agricultural sector is structured on the next axes:

- Axis 1 – Stimulating organic products consumption;
- Axis 2 – Stimulating production increase;
- Axis 3 – Continuous enhancing of organic agricultural sector sustainability.

Stimulating organic products increase in a sustainable way it is wanted, promoting the products and informing and increasing consumer trust by ensuring the traceability of the food value chain.

A key element to increase production is reaching the objective of using 25% of total used surface for organic farming and also encouraging organic tourism through local actors, and their cooperation for an efficient long term management of natural resources.

Continuous improvement of organic agricultural sector it is urgently needed, by measures that focus on livestock health, reducing carbon footprint in agricultural sector, maintaining biodiversity and by a rigorous management of essential resources (water, air, soil).

All of these objectives must become mandatory and be implemented at the national level by European countries, through local and regional authorities.

The European Union Strategy for Sustainable Development is the basis of Romania's National Strategy in the field. This strategy is being implemented in EU countries, with the involvement of local and regional authorities.

Graph 1. Total fully converted (hectares) and under conversion in Romania (2012–2020)

Source: <https://www.madr.ro/docs/agricultura/agricultura-ecologica/2021/Dinamica-operatorilor-si-a-suprafetelor-agri-eco-update-28.06.2021.pdf>

The organic farming sector is constantly evolving both globally and nationally. In Romania, organic agriculture has registered an ascending evolution in recent years. As of 2012, the ecological agricultural area was 288,261 ha. Compared to 2012, in 2019 the ecological agricultural area increased by almost 40%. Agricultural lands in Romania amount to a total area of 13.3 million ha, of which only 8.3 million ha. represents arable land, according to the latest data of the Ministry of Agriculture.

The ecological agricultural surface (468,887.05 ha.) represents only 3% of the total surface of the agricultural lands in Romania. This percentage places us at the end of the European Union states ranking, according to Eurostat data.

Graph 2. Total fully converted (hectares) and under conversion in UE (2012–2019)

Source: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=org_cropar&lang=en

In 2019, the total area of the European Union (EU) for organic crops was 14.25 million hectares, representing on average 8% of the total agricultural area used. This represents a significant increase of 34% compared to the situation in 2012, respectively from 10.04 million hectares to 14.25 million hectares, according to the same data source – Eurostat data.

In this context, assessing the current status of the organic sector in Romania, by power of the fact that we own the necessary resources and potential to increase supply of organic products internally, our country can be a possible supplier of agricultural products of high value and safety for the rest of European countries. The agricultural sector in Romania consists of small farms and households, the percentage destined for organic farming was only 2.9% in 2020 (according to MADR data, 2020), and might attain, by 2030, to the 25% of all farm land to be destined to organic farming.

CONCLUSIONS

Organic farming can combine best environmental practices, and can also help farmers adapt to climate change by diversifying agricultural production and improving agricultural ecosystems. In addition to obtaining quality food, it has other benefits, such as: responsible use

of pesticides and fertilizers and the use of alternative techniques in agriculture, conservation of water and soil fertility, ensuring animal welfare, conservation of biodiversity in agricultural crops and in ecosystems, and maintaining the economic stability of farms.

For the sustainability of agriculture, a balance must be found between the need for food production and the conservation of the ecological system. Organic farming must become one of the main vectors for maintaining biodiversity, food production and economic ecosystem services. The only drawback of this is that the yields are usually lower than in conventional agriculture. (Röös et al., 2018) The conclusion is that organic farming will produce enough food only if other aspects of the food system are changed at the same time (Muller et al. (2017).

In a complex agricultural policy, a well-developed agricultural system can mitigate climate change, maintain the economic stability of farms and farmers by improving the quality of life and is playing a key role in achieving the EU's goals set out in the "From Farm to Consumer" Strategy and the Biodiversity Strategy.

REFERENCES

- Altieri, M.A., Nicholls, C.I., Henao, A., & Lana, M.A.** (2015). Agroecology and the design of climate change-resilient farming systems. *Agronomy for sustainable development*, 35(3), 869–890.
- Battaglini, L., Bovolenta, S., Gusmeroli, F., Salvador, S., & Sturaro, E.** (2014). Environmental sustainability of Alpine livestock farms. *Italian Journal of Animal Science*, 13(2), 3155.
- Bernués, A., Ruiz, R., Olaizola, A., Villalba, D., & Casasús, I.** (2011). Sustainability of pasture-based livestock farming systems in the European Mediterranean context: Synergies and trade-offs. *Livestock Science*, 139(1–2), 44–57.
- Brundtland, G.H.** (1987). What is sustainable development. *Our common future*, 8(9).
- Cameron, K.C., Di, H.J., & Moir, J.L.** (2013). Nitrogen losses from the soil/plant system: a review. *Annals of applied biology*, 162(2), 145–173.
- Duru, M., Bastien, D., Froidmont, E., Graulet, B., Gruffat, D., & Saint-Genès-Champanelle, F.** (2017). Importance qualitative et quantitative des produits issus de bovins au pâturage sur les apports nutritionnels et la santé du consommateur. *Journées de Printemps de l'AFPP*, 131–140.
- FAO.** (2001). *The State of Food and Agriculture 2001* (No. 33). Food & Agriculture Org..
- Farruggia, A., Pomiès, D., Coppa, M., Ferlay, A., Verdier-Metz, I., Le Morvan, A., ... & Martin, B.** (2014). Animal performances, pasture biodiversity and dairy product quality: how it works in contrasted mountain grazing systems. *Agriculture, ecosystems & environment*, 185, 231–244.
- Franks, D.M., Davis, R., Bebbington, A.J., Ali, S.H., Kemp, D., & Scurrah, M.** (2014). Conflict translates environmental and social risk into business costs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(21), 7576–7581
- Frison, E.A., Cherfas, J., & Hodgkin, T.** (2011). Agricultural biodiversity is essential for a sustainable improvement in food and nutrition security. *Sustainability*, 3(1), 238–253.
- Gabriel, D., Carver, S.J., Durham, H., Kunin, W.E., Palmer, R.C., Sait, S.M., Stagl, S., Benton, T.G.,** 2009. The spatial aggregation of organic farming in England and its underlying environmental correlates. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 46, 323e333.
- Garbach, K., Milder, J.C., DeClerck, F.A., Montenegro de Wit, M., Driscoll, L., & Gemmill-Herren, B.** (2017). Examining multi-functionality for crop yield and ecosystem services in five systems of agroecological intensification. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 15(1), 11–28.

- Hammond, K.J., Humphries, D.J., Westbury, D.B., Thompson, A., Crompton, L.A., Kirton, P., ... & Reynolds, C. K.** (2014). The inclusion of forage mixtures in the diet of growing dairy heifers: Impacts on digestion, energy utilisation, and methane emissions. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 197, 88–95.
- IFOAM**, 2008 "Definition of organic agriculture" - <https://www.ifoam.bio/why-organic/organic-landmarks/definition-organic> – accessed on 01.10.2021
- IFOAM**, 2014 "Principles of organic agriculture" – <https://www.ifoam.bio/why-organic/shaping-agriculture/four-principles-organic> - accessed on 01.10.2021
- Jarvis, D.I., Hodgkin, T., Sthapit, B.R., Fadda, C., & Lopez-Noriega, I.** (2011). An heuristic framework for identifying multiple ways of supporting the conservation and use of traditional crop varieties within the agricultural production system. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 30(1–2), 125–176.
- Khanal RC** (2009). Climate Change and Organic Agriculture. *The Journal of Agriculture and Environment* 10:100–110.
- Kühl, S., Flach, L., & Gauly, M.** (2020). Economic assessment of small-scale mountain dairy farms in South Tyrol depending on feed intake and breed. *Italian Journal of Animal Science*, 19(1), 41–50.
- Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development – "Agriculture"; <https://www.madr.ro/docs/agricultura/agricultura-ecologica/2021/Dinamica-operatorilor-si-a-suprafetelor-agri-eco-update-28.06.2021.pdf> - accessed on 09.10.2021
- Muller, A., Schader, C., Scialabba, N.E.H., Brüggemann, J., Isensee, A., Erb, K.H., ... & Niggli, U.** (2017). Strategies for feeding the world more sustainably with organic agriculture. *Nature communications*, 8(1), 1–13.
- Nagler, M., Fontana, V., Lair, G. J., Radtke, A., Tasser, E., Zerbe, S., & Tappeiner, U.** (2015). Different management of larch grasslands in the European Alps shows low impact on above- and belowground carbon stocks. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 213, 186–193.
- European Parliament – "Biodiversity loss: the problem and the causes" - <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/ro/headlines/society/20200109STO69929/pierderea-biodiversitatii-problema-si-cauzele> – accessed on 05.10.2021
- European Parliament – "EU agriculture and climate change" – accessed on 25.09.2021
https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy/new-cap-2023-27/key-policy-objectives-new-cap_ro
https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=org_croprop&lang=en
- Ponisio LC, M'Gonigle LK, Mace KC, Palomino J, de Valpine P, Kremen C** (2015) Diversification practices reduce organic to conventional yield gap. *Proc R Soc B* 282:20141396.
- Röös, E., Mie, A., Wivstad, M., Salomon, E., Johansson, B., Gunnarsson, S., ... & Watson, C. A.** (2018). Risks and opportunities of increasing yields in organic farming. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 38(2), 1–21.
- Seufert, V., Ramankutty, N. & Foley, J.A.** (2012) Comparing the yields of organic and conventional agriculture. *Nature*, 485, 229–232.
- Tasser, E., Walde, J., Tappeiner, U., Teutsch, A., & Noggler, W.** (2007). Land-use changes and natural reforestation in the Eastern Central Alps. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 118(1–4), 115–129.
- Tendall, D.M., Joerin, J., Kopainsky, B., Edwards, P., Shreck, A., Le, Q.B., Kruetli, P., Grant, M., Six, J.** (2015). Food system resilience: Defining the concept. *Glob. Food Secur.* 6, 17–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2015.08.001>
- Therond, O., Duru, M., Roger-Estrade, J., & Richard, G.** (2017). A new analytical framework of farming system and agriculture model diversities. A review. *Agronomy for sustainable development*, 37(3), 1–24.

- Thomassen, M.A., Dolman, M.A., Van Calker, K.J., & De Boer, I.J.M.** (2009). Relating life cycle assessment indicators to gross value added for Dutch dairy farms. *Ecological Economics*, 68(8/9), 2278–2284.
- Veysset, P., Lherm, M., Boussemart, J.P., & Natier, P.** (2019). Generation and distribution of productivity gains in beef cattle farming: Who are the winners and losers between 1980 and 2015?. *animal*, 13(5), 1063–1073.
- Willer, H., Sampson, G., Voora, V., Dang, D., & Lernoud, J.** (2019). *The State of Sustainable Markets 2019 – Statistics and Emerging Trends*. International Trade Centre (ITC), International Institute for Sustainable (IISD), Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL).